

Optimization of Bamboo Fibre Reinforcement in Green Composites using Response Surface Methodology

Jigar Suthar^a, Disha Suthar^{b*}

^a Assistant Professor, Department of Mechanical Engineering, LDRP institute of Technology and Research, Kadi Sarva Vishwavidyalaya

^{b*} Professor, Department of Pharmaceutics, Sharda School of Pharmacy, Gujarat Technological University.

*Corresponding Author

Address: Opp. Kailash Dham, Pethapur - Mahudi, Road, Pethapur, Gandhinagar, Gujarat 382610

Abstract

Bamboo is an ancient structural material used for a variety of applications in India. Bamboo is widely used in the global south for frames, bridges, housing, and transitory structures. Bamboo supply has been effectively inexpensive as well as plentiful in global south countries to meet the widespread need for affordable housing. The current research focuses on the mechanical properties of bamboo fibre reinforced polymer composite materials for use in structural industries. Current study aims to optimize a composite with optimal tensile strength. A 3 level 2 factor full factorial design was prepared considering % bamboo fibre loading as factor A and diameter of bamboo fibre as factor B. The study evaluated the impact of factor A and B on ultimate tensile strength, Rockwell hardness and % elongation at break. The optimized region was prepared keeping the ultimate tensile strength to 35-40MPa, rockwell hardness in the region of 30-35 and the % elongation to 2-2.5%. Prepared optimized batch was then validated by comparing predicted and observed response values.

Key Words: Green composites, Bamboo fibre, 3² full factorial design, Optimization, Response surface methodology

1.Introduction

Materials are recognized as the cornerstone of the manufacturing sector which uses a wide range of composites, alloys, and pure metals. As pure metals are unable to match the demands of current products, focus is being moved to the employment of composites[1]. Composites are one of the most commonly utilized materials in today's manufacturing sector, increasingly replacing their traditional equivalents due to their promising properties, which include great strength, outstanding damping capacity, and high specific modulus. In the 1920s, composite materials were first developed by adding fiber reinforcement. Multiphase materials made composed of two components or more with distinct properties are called composite materials [2].

One of the significant challenges is demonstrating that the behavior of epoxy composites is significantly affected by the partial addition of bamboo fiber powder, since the powder's uniform dispersion can strengthen the bond and improve the mechanical properties of epoxy composites. Bamboo is a low-cost, lightweight, flexible, strong, and high-tensile material that can be used in the building and furniture sectors, especially for packing, shipping, and domestic use[3].

In developing countries like Malaysia, Indonesia, Thailand, and other Asian countries, NFs are very prevalent. Commonly utilized natural fibers include bamboo, rice husk, and kenaf. Bamboo is a cost-effective and rapidly growing plant that is a great raw material for many different industries, including polymer composites. Bamboo fiber is particularly alluring because it is widely accessible and reasonably priced. But like other NFs, BF degrades around about 200°C, therefore its low thermal stability poses a significant problem[4].

In order to find the best way to treat bamboo fibers, Liu Lijuan et al. created bio composites utilizing Bambusa tulda and cashew nut shell oil-based bio-epoxy resin at different NaOH concentrations (2, 4, 6, 8, and 10%). Fiber weight fractions ranging from 10% to 40% were used to create composites. Similarly, by treating bamboo strips with NaOH solutions (5, 8, 12, and 15%) for 12 hours, they also examined the mechanical characteristics of BF/epoxy composites made by compression molding and hand lay-up procedures[5]. According to their research, compression molding yielded composites with better mechanical qualities than the hand lay-up approach, and bamboo fibre strips treated with NaOH at 8, 12, and 15% were more compatible with the resin[6].

The response surface methodology (RSM) is a potent statistical technique for enhancing the experimental characteristics of natural fiber composites. Box-Behnken Design (BBD), central composite design (CCD), and 3-level factorial designs are examples of common RSM methodologies. Current studies involve the application of 3-level factorial designs to optimize the % loading of bamboo fibres and the diameter of bamboo fibres to achieve optimum mechanical strength of prepared composite materials[7].

2. Materials and Methods:

2.1. Bamboo Fibre

Bamboo cultivated in Gujarat's Dang district provided the fibers used in this investigation. The preliminary trials yielded positive results, thus a mix of chemical and mechanical approaches were used to remove the long fibers. Prior to being crushed by a crusher, bamboos that were cut longer than the specimen's needed length (165 mm) were allowed to dry in the sun for two weeks. The bamboos were then let to soak for an hour at room temperature in a 5% NaOH solution. The solution was then removed from the fiber surface by washing the fibers four times with distilled water and dried in oven at 80°C for 5 hours [8].

2.2. Epoxy Resin

Chimique sol Pvt.Ltd. (Surat, Gujarat) supplied viscous epoxy resin and curing agents (brand Chimique sol-Csclear).

2.3. Fabrication of Fibre reinforced composites

A mold with a volume of 180 x 180 x 3 mm³ was used to create the composite plate. Before the fibers were inserted, the mold was sprayed with 8329 epoxy mold release agent to stop the metal mold and composite from bonding. The bubbles that formed when the fluid was poured into the mold were eliminated using a propane flame. After that, the composite plate was left to cure for eight hours at room temperature. After that, the mold was heated to 60 degrees Celsius for three hours in a press molding machine[8].

2.4. Application of Response Surface Methodology

A 3 level 2 factor full factorial design was selected. Two independent variables namely % fibre loading (%) and diameter of bamboo fibre were considered as factor A and factor B whereas, ultimate tensile strength, Rockwell hardness and % elongation at break were selected as dependent variables. All samples were prepared as the layout suggested in Table 1 and were evaluated.[9]

Results were evaluated by the software and optimization was performed to achieve optimum tensile strength, Rockwell hardness and % elongation at break[10].

2.5 Measurement of Ultimate tensile strength

An ASTM D638-10 universal testing equipment was used to measure the tensile strength. Every specimen was operated at 50% humidity and room temperature with a cross head speed of 5 mm/min. For every composite, three samples were tested, and the average values are noted for further examination[11].

2.6. Measurement of Rockwell Hardness

To ascertain the material's strength and resistance to wear, a Rockwell hardness test was also conducted in compliance with ASTM E18[12].

2.7. Measurement of %Elongation at break

An ASTM D638-10 universal testing equipment was used to measure the tensile strength. Every specimen was operated at 50% humidity and room temperature with a cross head speed of 5 mm/min. For every composite, three samples were tested, and the average values are noted for further examination[13].

Result and Discussion

3.1. Application of Response Surface Methodology

Table 1 depicts the overall summary of design batches along with the results. The results were evaluated further for ANOVA [14]and other statistical parameters discussed further.

Table I. Experimental pattern and results of full factorial design

	Factor 1	Factor 2	Response 1	Response 2	Response 3
Run	A:%Fibre loading	B:Diameter of fibre	Ultimate tensile strength	Rockwell Hardness	%Elongation at break
	%	micrometer	MPa	RHN	%
1	14.5	0.5	41.26	32.23	2.6
2	14.5	0.25	38.56	29.63	1.55
3	12	0.25	26.51	16.52	1.23
4	12	0.75	40.21	33.24	1.45
5	17	0.75	27.23	18.52	2.35
6	17	0.5	35.24	27.23	2.25
7	12	0.5	38.1	30.12	1.38
8	14.5	0.75	40.12	34.23	1.89
9	17	0.25	36.21	28.96	2.9

3.2. Model fitting and ANOVA analysis for ultimate tensile strength

Table II: ANOVA summary for ultimate tensile strength

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	p-value	
Model	238.01	5	47.60	49.58	0.0044	significant
A-%Fibre loading	6.28	1	6.28	6.54	0.0833	
B-Diameter of fibre	6.57	1	6.57	6.85	0.0792	

AB	128.60	1	128.60	133.95	0.0014	
A ²	73.53	1	73.53	76.59	0.0031	
B ²	23.03	1	23.03	23.99	0.0163	
Residual	2.88	3	0.9601			
Cor Total	240.89	8				

P-values less than 0.0500 indicate model terms are significant. In this case AB, A², B² are significant model terms. Values greater than 0.1000 indicate the model terms are not significant. The Predicted R² of 0.8971 is in reasonable agreement with the Adjusted R² of 0.9681; i.e. the difference is less than 0.2.

In the polynomial equation the factors with positive sign suggest synergistic effect with respect to response while the factors with negative sign suggest antagonistic effect of the factor in the response. The polynomial equation for ultimate tensile strength is shown below.

$$UTS = 42.2422 + -1.02333 * A + 1.04667 * B + -5.67 * AB + -6.06333 * A^2 + -3.39333 * B^2$$

3.3. Model fitting and ANOVA for Rockwell Hardness

Table III: ANOVA summary for Rockwell Hardness

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	p-value	
Model	305.22	5	61.04	20.18	0.0162	significant
A-%Fibre loading	4.45	1	4.45	1.47	0.3118	
B-Diameter of fibre	19.73	1	19.73	6.52	0.0837	
AB	184.42	1	184.42	60.96	0.0044	
A ²	78.50	1	78.50	25.95	0.0146	
B ²	18.12	1	18.12	5.99	0.0919	
Residual	9.08	3	3.03			
Cor Total	314.30	8				

P-values less than 0.0500 indicate model terms are significant. In this case AB, A² are significant model terms. Values greater than 0.1000 indicate the model terms are not significant. The Predicted R² of 0.7590 is in reasonable agreement with the Adjusted R² of 0.9230; i.e. the difference is less than 0.2 which further validates the response. While the polynomial equation establishing the relationship of factors with response for Rockwell hardness is mentioned below.

$$\text{Rockwell Hardness} = 34.0367 + -0.861667 * A + 1.81333 * B + -6.79 * AB + -6.265 * A^2 + -3.01 * B^2$$

3.3. Model fitting and ANOVA for % Elongation at break

Table IV: ANOVA summary for % Elongation at break

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	p-value	
Model	1.97	2	0.9861	6.89	0.0280	significant
A-%Fibre loading	1.97	1	1.97	13.77	0.0100	
B-Diameter of fibre	0.0000	1	0.0000	0.0001	0.9917	
Residual	0.8593	6	0.1432			
Cor Total	2.83	8				

ANOVA table clarifies that the % elongation follows linear model, which concludes the impact of independent parameters on the response and no impact of interaction terms. Further, it also suggest that %fibre loading plays significant role on the %Elongation as it can be concluded by the polynomial equation.

$$\% \text{Elongation at break} = 1.95556 + 0.573333 * A + 0.00166667 * B$$

3.4 Optimization

Figure I show the summary of individual contour plots of responses along with an overlay plot used for optimization of independent variables. Figure i(a) represents the contour plot suggesting the relationship between independent variables and ultimate tensile strength. While figure i(b) depicts the relationship between independent variables and rockwell hardness and the figure i(c) indicates the relationship between independent variables and %elongation at break. figure i(d) represents the overlay plot considering the factors incorporated for optimization. The yellow segment shown in figure i(d) is the optimize region where the composite can be fabricated with optimal tensile strength, rockwell hardness and % elongation.

Further the validation of optimized batch was done by preparing the composite form optimized region and the results were compared with predicted results by the software and it was found that the observed responses equivalent to predicted responses and the % error was found to be less than 5% concluding the validation of prepared design[15].

Figure 1. Figure i(a) contour plot suggesting the relationship between independent variables and ultimate tensile strength, i(b) relationship between independent variables and rockwell hardness and the figure i(c) relationship between independent variables and %elongation at break. figure i(d) overlay plot for optimization

4. Conclusion

Bamboo has shown to be a plentiful and reasonably priced resource to help address the growing demand for affordable composites without compromising the strength of material. The mechanical characteristics of bamboo fiber reinforced polymer composite materials for usage in structural industries are the main focus of the current study. Optimizing a composite with the best tensile strength is the goal of the current study. A three-level, two-factor full factorial design was created, with the diameter of the bamboo fiber as factor B and the percentage of bamboo fiber loading as factor A. The study assessed how factors A and B affected the percentage of % elongation at break, Rockwell hardness, and ultimate tensile strength using various statistical tools along with ANOVA. The contour plots were generated depicting the relationship of

independent variables with dependent variables. Optimization was done to achieve optimum tensile strength, % elongation and rockwell hardness.

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